

Offering CAMARA APIs as a Service - Demo

Rafael Direito^{*}, Kostis Trantzas[†], Diogo Gomes[‡], Christos Tranoris[§], Rui L. Aguiar[¶],

^{*}[‡][¶] Instituto de Telecomunicações and University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

[†][§] University of Patras, Patras, Greece

^{*}rdireito@av.it.pt, [†]ktrantzas@ece.upatras.gr, [‡]dgomes@av.it.pt, [§]tranoris@ece.upatras.gr [¶]ruilaa@av.it.pt

Abstract—The evolution of 5G and B5G technologies introduced high levels of programmability, control, and flexibility to wireless networks. However, the integration of these capabilities with industry-specific applications still remains challenge. The CAMARA initiative addresses this by standardizing APIs to simplify the interaction between applications and 5G/B5G network functionalities. Our demonstration introduces the concept of CAMARA APIs as a Service, an approach that enables telecommunication operators and service providers to offer these APIs with minimal development effort. We showcase how telecom operators can address Quality on Demand use cases through the ordering of a CAMARA API to manage the QoS of User Equipment within a 5G standalone commercial graded network. This demonstration highlights the potential of CAMARA as a Service to accelerate the adoption of CAMARA APIs and enhance the programmability of 5G/B5G services for the various industries.

Index Terms—CAMARA, CAMARAaaS, TM Forum, 5G

I. Introduction

The advent of 5G and B5G technologies represents a milestone in the advancement of wireless communication systems. These technologies are designed to deliver (i) enhanced capacity, (ii) reduced latency, and (iii) unique levels of programmability, (iv) control, and (v) flexibility [1]. These features are crucial to meet the growing demands of innovative use cases across various vertical sectors: specific sectors/industries that have specific requirements that can be addressed through tailored 5G/B5G solutions. Still, for these verticals to fully capitalize on the potential of 5G and B5G, they need to overcome the challenge of integrating their unique requirements with these networks' control and management capabilities.

Moreover, a long-lasting objective of 5G and B5G technologies is to enable the creation and operation of intelligent and highly adaptable networks. Therefore, 3GPP is heavily invested in standardizing the communication interfaces between vertical clients and the control plane of these networks [2], ensuring they benefit from the 5G/B5G programmability.

To address the complexities of interacting with 3GPP-defined interfaces, various initiatives focusing on simplifying the interaction between vertical clients and the 5G and B5G control planes have emerged.

One of the most promising initiatives tackling this issue is the CAMARA Project ¹. This project aims to respond to the crucial needs of vertical industries: enabling software developers to access complex network functions and services with simplicity. CAMARA APIs abstract the underlying network control complexities, empowering developers to focus on innovation, while fostering a unified ecosystem. The main goals of the CAMARA Project are the following: (i) simplifying telco complexity, by making APIs easy to consume for customers with no telco expertise, (ii) facilitate application to network integration, and

(iii) support application portability. Therefore, CAMARA APIs are being widely adopted by major telecommunication operators and cloud providers to enable seamless integration between applications and network capabilities. Among the various use cases where CAMARA APIs can be employed, we highlight location and quality-on-demand ones. Under these use cases, operators can opt to offer CAMARA APIs to the application developers within the 5G environment. Such APIs can abstract complex interactions with the 5G Policy Control Function and Location Management Function, therefore simplifying data consumption and control operations, making it easier for application developers to integrate advanced network capabilities without requiring deep expertise in telecommunication technologies.

In parallel with CAMARA, the 3GPP Common API Framework (CAPIF) is another initiative that aims to offer a framework for accessing 3GPP northbound APIs, by streamlining their discovery, exposure, and consumption. The adoption of CAMARA and CAPIF is seen not only as a technical enhancement but as a paradigm shift in how network functions and services are consumed, highlighting the importance of industry standards for addressing innovative use cases.

This demonstration introduces the concept of CAMARA as a Service (CAMARAaaS): an approach that enables telecom operators and customer service providers to expose already existing network services through CAMARA standardized endpoints. By leveraging CAMARAaaS, service providers can enhance their service offerings without the need for extensive modifications to their underlying systems. Moreover, for offering such APIs, ETSI's OpenSlice (OSL) can be employed: an Operations Support System (OSS) that offers various TM Forum (TMF) Northbound APIs. It is worth mentioning that CAMARA APIs can also be offered through the CAPIF framework, resulting in their controlled exposure and consumption. Thus, this demonstration integrates various standards and industry specifications to achieve the offering of straightforward APIs to manage 5G/B5G resources.

II. System Design and Architecture

The CAMARAaaS approach we introduce in this demonstration assumes that network services can be exposed through TMF APIs. These APIs are domain-agnostic and provide standardized interfaces to facilitate the offering and runtime control of services/resources. Examples of these APIs are the TMF Service Catalog Management, Service Order Management, and Service Inventory Management APIs. Altogether, these APIs enable (i) the exposure of a Service through a catalog, (ii) its ordering, and (iii) lifecycle management. Therefore, it is possible to expose, for instance, a 5G Core and a 5G RAN, through TMF APIs, which is also addressed in this demonstration. For this specific use case, CAMARA APIs can integrate with TMF ones to offer straightforward and standardized interfaces to manage 5G-related resources. Moreover, by wrapping 5G-specific APIs with CAMARA, it be-

¹<https://camaraproject.org/>

Fig. 1: CAMARAaaS Architectural Approach

comes possible to provide simple and unified interfaces to control the custom resources offered by various vendors and operators.

Considering that TMF APIs are widely adopted as an industry standard, one can leverage them to offer CAMARA operations. To this end, we propose relying on middleware layers to translate CAMARA API requests into TMF API Service operations. With this approach, telecom operators may expose an existing 5G-related resource/service through CAMARA APIs, without having to explicitly delve into their implementation, resulting in the expedited offering of these APIs, by these operators.

In order to achieve the previously introduced middleware layers we can rely on the TMF 638 - Service Inventory Management API, as it provides an interface to control the lifecycle of already running Services. Therefore, our approach can rely on a middleware that translates CAMARA requests to TMF 638 ones. The architectural approach that allows for the offering of this middleware is introduced in Figure 1.

This architecture assumes the existence of an already running 5G Core Service, exposed through TMF APIs. To manage this resource through CAMARA APIs, the first step is to order the deployment of the Middleware Service, referencing the UUID of the service to be controlled. Upon deployment of the middleware, a CAMARA REST API is made available and exposed. It is through this API that it becomes possible to manage the initial 5G Core Service. When CAMARA API requests are received by the middleware, they are translated to TMF 638 requests, enforced on the 5G Core Service, and their outcomes are collected offered through the newly exposed API (see Figure 1).

This approach enables the offering of CAMARA APIs as a Service. Telecom operators and service providers are not required to implement them, but can rather request them as add-on Services, in order to control already existing Services. Additionally, CAPIF can be employed to expose such APIs and ensure their controlled consumption. To this end, we can rely on ETSI's OpenCAPIF initiative, even though we see this as future work.

III. Demonstration

In this demonstration, we showcase how the Quality of Service (QoS) of already existing 5G User Equipment (UE) can be controlled through a CAMARA REST API. The 5G Infrastructure that supports this demonstration is named 5GAIner [3], and it provides a commercial-graded standalone 5G network, offered through various 5G new radio cells, as well as a Huawei 5G Core that adheres to 3GPP Release 17 standards. All these resources can be managed through proprietary APIs

[4], wrapped by TMF ones, which enables a standardized way of exposing an interacting with them. With respect to employed 5G UE, we relied on Huawei P40 Pro 5G Smartphones. Additionally, this demonstration showcases the CAMARA Quality on Demand (QoD) Provisioning API. This API is used to provision specific QoS profiles for individual UE in a straightforward manner.

Regarding the ordering and offering of both the 5G Services and the CAMARA Middleware, we rely on OSL, an OSS currently under the umbrella of an ETSI Software Development Group. It offers various TMF compliant northbound APIs, thus being the ideal candidate to offer our CAMARAaaS approach.

The demonstration starts with the ordering, via OSL, of a custom UE Profile Enforcer Service, wrapped by a Kubernetes Custom Resource (CR), that bridges with the 5GAIner infrastructure. Through OSL's CRIDGE component, the UE Profile Enforcer CR is deployed on Kubernetes and exposed through TMF APIs. Later, we order a CAMARAaaS API - the QoD Provisioning one - which will also be deployed through CRIDGE. When both services are running, we will demonstrate the integration between these two services, as well as one can enforce specific UE QoS profiles by leveraging the CAMARA API exposed by OSL. A video showcasing this demonstration is available at [5].

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the European Union / Next Generation EU, through Programa de Recuperação e Resiliência (PRR) [Project Nr. 783: A NextGen Mobility (07/C16-i02/2022.P783)] and by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program through the Project IMAGINE-B5G (Grant 101096452).

References

- [1] R. Dangi, P. Lalwani, G. Choudhary, I. You, and G. Pau, "Study and investigation on 5g technology: A systematic review," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2022.
- [2] 3GPP, "3GPP TS 26.531 V18.2.0 - Data Collection and Reporting; General Description and Architecture (Release 18)," 3GPP, Tech. Rep., June 2024.
- [3] J. Quevedo, A. Perdigão, D. Santos, R. Silva, and R. L. Aguiar, "5GAIner: Taking the verticals into the 5G road," in *2023 EuCNC/6G Summit*, 2023, pp. 514–519.
- [4] A. Perdigão, J. Quevedo, and R. L. Aguiar, "Automating 5g network slice management for industrial applications," *Computer Communications*, vol. 229, p. 107991, 2025.
- [5] R. Direito, K. Trantzas, D. Gomes, C. Tranoris, and R. Aguiar, "Offering camara apis as a service - demonstration," Feb. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14900491>